

INDEX NUMBER.....

HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019
RM 16: HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Communication is said to have a role in changing behaviours

- a. What is communication - 2 marks
- b. What are the three (3) determinants of behavior change - 3marks
- c. Explain the five (5) stages of behavior change in an adult learner - 10marks
- d. Enumerate five (5) characteristics of an adult learner - 5marks

QUESTION TWO

The process of your entry into a community determines the success and failure of your work

- a. What is Community entry? - 3 marks
- b. Explain the three (3) ways the nurse is expected to prepare towards official entry into a community - 6 marks
- c. State six (6) steps in community entry - 6 marks
- d. State five (5) importance of community study - 5 marks

QUESTION THREE

The process of community diagnosis involves four stages

- a. State the four (4) stages of community diagnosis - 4 marks
- b. Explain the four stages stated above - 8 marks
- c. Define community diagnosis - 2 marks
- d. State and explain three types of needs - 6 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- a. Explain the following in your own words
 - i. Community- Client Oriented Provider Efficient - 2 marks
 - ii. Gender mainstreaming - 2 marks
 - iii. Community mobilization - 2 marks
 - iv. Stigma - 2 marks
- b. Explain the steps you will follow in planning health promotion programme - 12marks

HFNMTC- BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – 22ND SEPTEMBER, 2021
(RGN 23/RM18) RGN 123/ RMD122: HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 1HR 30MINUTES
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

Nurse Akuamoah, a public health nurse is preparing to have health promotion/education programme with Domiebra community on their health behaviour. The community is known for throwing away both wet and dry refuse indiscriminately.

- a. What is behaviour change? - 3MARKS
- b. What are the three (3) determinants of behavior change - 3MARKS
- c. Explain four (4) stages of behavior change - 8MARKS
- d. State six (6) steps in community entry - 6MARKS

Question Two

- a. You have been tasked to explain the process of community diagnosis to a first-year nursing student.
 - i. Explain the four stages of community diagnosis - 8MARKS
 - ii. Define community diagnosis - 2MARKS
- b. Stigmatization has been identified as one of the social factors affecting health care delivery in the country which needs to be addressed if the goal of achieving health for all is to be realized.
 - i. State five factors that lead to fear and stigma - 5 MARKS
 - ii. State five effects of stigmatization on individual - 5 MARKS

Question Three

- a. Adwoa Boatemaa, a 26-year-old lady is engaged to Mr. Berko and later planned to get married after five years of dating. Two weeks to the wedding, Mr. Berko broke up with Adwoa Boatemaa, and this made her unable to cope with events of life leading to the feeling of guilt, anxiety, depression and self-destruction. She was therefore taken to a psychiatry hospital where she was referred to see a counselor for crisis counseling.
 - i. Mention 5 dimensions of health that you know - 5MARKS
 - ii. Indicate three determinants of health - 3MARKS
- b. Explain the GATHER approach to counseling - 12 MARKS

SR. MARGARET AFRIFA

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - APRIL, 2013
DIPLOMA (15) & RM 10 HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 2Hrs.

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

Health is said to be a process in which all the parts of a person's life work together in integrated way.

DISCUSS - 20 marks

Questions Two

Describe the following terms as used in Health Promotion.

- a. Health and Balance state - 5 marks
- b. Health and lifestyle - 5 marks
- c. Theory of general susceptibility - 5 marks
- d. Germ theory of disease causation - 5marks

Question Three

Define the following;

- a. i. Health Promotion - 2 marks
- ii. Health Education - 2 marks
- b. State four (4) factors that can influence the health of an individual - 4 marks
- c. State and explain three (3) models one can use for effective Health Education / Health Program - 12 marks

Question Four

Kwadwo Badukrom is a village in the Brong Ahafo Region. The major problem here is indiscriminate waste disposal and

This affects their health. How are you going to act towards promoting health in Kwadwo Badukrom.

- 20 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
DIPLOMA I6/RM II HRGN024/ HMDW 037 HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. Define the following terms as used in Health Education / Health Promotion
- i. Health Education - 2 marks
 - ii. Health promotion - 2 marks
 - iii. WHO definition of health - 2 marks
- b. Explain the four (4) key principles of health promotion as determined by WHO - 8 marks
- c. State four (4) main determinants of Health - 4 marks
- d. List two (2) skills of health promotion action - 2 marks

Question Two

- a. As a student nurse, you have been asked to conduct a community study at Kwame Danso in the Brong Ahafo Region.
- i. What is community study - 2 marks
 - ii. State the three (3) types of community study - 3 marks
 - iii. State the preparations you will make before community entry - 3 marks
 - iv. State three (3) importance of needs assessment - 3 marks
- b. People living with HIV/AIDS are stigmatized
- i. What is stigma? - 2 marks
 - ii. Mention two types of stigma - 2 marks
 - iii. In what five (5) ways can stigma be challenged - 5 marks

Question Three

An adult is said to learn differently from a child

- a. Define the following terms
- i. Andragogy - 1 mark
 - ii. Pedagogy - 1 mark
- b. Draw the experiential learning cycle - 4 marks
- c. Explain each phase of the experiential learning cycle - 8 marks
- d. List six (6) characteristics of effective learning - 6 marks

Question Four

For effective and efficient health education/promotion programme, there is the need for effective interpersonal communication

- a. What is interpersonal communication? - 2 marks
- b. Identify and explain the determinants of behavior change - 6 marks
- c. State the six (6) steps of effective counseling - 3 marks
- d. Identify six (6) benefits of using Behaviour Change Communication materials - 6 marks
- e. Mention three (3) advantages of using video tape - 3 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - APRIL, 2013
DIPLOMA (15) & RM 10 HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 2Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
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Question One

Health is said to be a process in which all the parts of a person's life work together in integrated way.

Discuss - 20 marks

Questions Two

Describe the following terms as used in Health Promotion.

- a. Health and Balance state - 5 marks
- b. Health and lifestyle - 5 marks
- c. Theory of general susceptibility - 5 marks
- d. Germ theory of disease causation - 5marks

Question Three

Define the following:

- i. Health Promotion - 2 marks
- ii. Health Education - 2 marks
- b. State four (4) factors that can influence the health of an individual - 4 marks
- c. State and explain three (3) models one can use for effective Health Education / Health Program - 12 marks

Question Four

Kwadwo Badukrom is a village in the Brong Ahafo Region. The major problem here is indiscriminate waste disposal and

This affects their health. How are you going to act towards promoting health in Kwadwo Badukrom.

- 20 marks

NMTC- BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY 2016
D 18 & RM 13: HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS
ESSAY

Instruction:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

Question One

Miss Cinderella, a 26 year old staff nurse is engaged to Mr. Pinto and they later planned to get married. Two weeks to the wedding, Mr. Pinto broke up with Miss Cinderella and this made Cinderella unable to cope with events of life leading to the feeling of guilt, anxiety, depression and self destruction. She was therefore taken to a psychiatry hospital where she was referred to see a counselor for crisis counseling.

- | | | |
|--|---|---------|
| a. What is crisis counseling | - | 1 mark |
| b. State four characteristics of an ideal counseling environment | - | 4 marks |
| c. State the six steps in effective counseling | - | 6 marks |
| d. State and briefly explain in NOT more than two sentences the stages of the structural aspect of the counseling\ | | |
| e. process | - | 6 marks |
| f. State the three factors affecting interpersonal communication | - | 3 marks |

Question Two

Stigmatization has been identified as one of the social factors affecting health care delivery in the country which needs to be addressed if the goal of achieving health for all is to be realized.

- | | | |
|---|---|---------|
| a. Define the term stigmatization | - | 1 mark |
| b. State five factors that lead to fear and stigma | - | 5 marks |
| c. State five effects of stigmatization on health care delivery | - | 5 marks |
| d. State five ways to combat stigma | - | 5 marks |
| e. State four benefits of living in a world without stigma | - | 4 marks |

Question Three

Health promotion programmes will be successful if planned carefully. As the nurse in-charge of health education/promotion in your district, you have been tasked to carry out health education on solid waste management which is a major issue confronting the people of your district. How are you going to plan for the success of this health promotion activity? 20 marks

Question Four

At Brenyekwa, a suburb of Berekum community, there is a major problem with solid waste disposal. The problem is that solid waste is found scattered all over the place. Children can be found playing at the rubbish dump and using some as toys. During cholera outbreaks, the community suffers since most of its members become affected leading to death among some.

It has come to the notice of Berekum District Assembly that the community has a major health problem that needed addressing through the District Office of health. You as the nurse in – charge of health education/promotion at Brenyekwa has been called upon to manage this problem.

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|--|---|---------|
| a. By applying the health promotion actions / strategies how will you act towards promoting health at Brenyekwa. | - | 15marks |
| b. Explain the experiential learning cycle | - | 5 marks |

NMTC- BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY 2016
D 18 & RM 13: HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

ESSAY

Instruction:

- Answer all questions
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Question One

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- a. What is crisis counseling - 1 mark
- b. State four characteristics of an ideal counseling environment - 4 marks
- c. State the six steps in effective counseling - 6 marks
- d. State and briefly explain in NOT more than two sentences the stages of the structural aspect of the counseling process - 6 marks
- e. State the three factors affecting interpersonal communication - 3 marks

Question Two

Stigmatization has been identified as one of the social factors affecting health care delivery in the country which needs to be addressed if the goal of achieving health for all is to be realized.

- a. Define the term stigmatization - 1 mark
- b. State five factors that lead to fear and stigma - 5 marks
- c. State five effects of stigmatization on health care delivery - 5 marks
- d. State five ways to combat stigma - 5 marks
- e. State four benefits of living in a world without stigma - 4 marks

Question Three

Health promotion programmes will be successful if planned carefully. As the nurse in-charge of health education/promotion in your district, you have been tasked to carry out health education on solid waste management which is a major issue confronting the people of your district. How are you going to plan for the success of this health promotion activity? - 20 marks

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At Brenyekwa, a suburb of Berekum community, there is a major problem with solid waste disposal. The problem is that solid waste is found scattered all over the place. Children can be found playing at the rubbish dump and using some as toys. During cholera outbreaks, the community suffers since most of its members become affected leading to death among some.

It has come to the notice of Berekum District Assembly that the community has a major health problem that needed addressing through the District Office of health. You as the nurse in – charge of health education/promotion at Brenyekwa has been called upon to manage this problem.

- a. By applying the health promotion actions / strategies how will you act towards promoting health at Brenyekwa. - 15marks
- b. Explain the experiential learning cycle - 5 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM / ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2017
19 / RM 14 RGN123/ RMD 122 HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
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- Each question carries 20 marks.
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Question One

- a. Define the following terms
 - i. Health (WHO definition) - 2marks
 - ii. Health promotion - 2marks
- b. What is meant by gender mainstreaming - 2marks
- c. What is behaviour change - 2marks
- d. Identify and explain FOUR(4) determinants of health - 12marks

Question Two

Emelia Frimpong a 22 years old girl who fails her semester examination has been sad and it is affecting her performance. Emelia is therefore referred to the counselling unit for assistance.

- a. What is counselling - 2marks
- b. Give four differences between counselling and interpersonal communication - 8marks
- c. Discuss the six steps in effective counselling - 9marks
- d. State any TWO (2) information, education and communication materials - 1marks

Question Three

- a. Stigmatization has been identified as one of the social factors affecting health care delivery in the country
 - i. Define stigmatization - 2marks
 - ii. State any two (2) types of stigma - 2marks
 - iii. Give five (5) effects/consequences of stigma on the -
 - iv. State any four ways to combat stigma - 4marks
 - v. State the process of stigma - 2marks
- b. Explain each phase of the experiential learning cycle - 8marks
- c. State any FOUR(4) teaching methods that can be employed to promote learner centred learning - 2 Marks

Question Four

As a newly posted nurse to Fetentaa health centre, you realised that most of the children attending the centre were malnourished. Therefore you became more interested in finding out the root cause of the problem and realised that the children in the community are not fed with balance diet.

- a. Explain how you will plan your health promotion programme to solve the problem - 20marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
DIPLOMA 16/RM 11 HRGN024/HMDW 037 HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs.
ESSAY

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